

Diagnostic Accuracy of Ultrasound for Placenta Accreta Spectrum (PAS) Disorder: Correlation with Surgical and Neonatal Outcomes

Sneh Priya¹, Madhuri Kumari², Chandra Bhushan Singh³

¹MBBS, MD, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Senior Resident DMCH, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

²MBBS, MD, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Senior Resident, AIIMS, Delhi, India

³MBBS, MD, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Senior Resident, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Chandra Bhushan Singh

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Abstract:

Background: Placenta Accreta Spectrum (PAS) disorder is a serious obstetric condition characterized by abnormal placental attachment, leading to increased maternal morbidity and mortality. Accurate prenatal diagnosis, primarily through ultrasound, is crucial for planning appropriate management strategies and improving maternal and neonatal outcomes.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound in detecting PAS disorder and to assess the correlation between ultrasound findings, surgical outcomes, and neonatal health.

Methods: The study analyzed the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) of ultrasound in diagnosing PAS. Additionally, the correlation between ultrasound findings and surgical outcomes, such as estimated blood loss (EBL) and the necessity of hysterectomy and neonatal outcomes, was assessed using statistical methods in SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Ultrasound identified PAS in 78 out of 100 cases, with surgical confirmation in 85 cases. The sensitivity and specificity of ultrasound were 91.8% and 68.2%, respectively, with a PPV of 82.1% and an NPV of 81.5%. There was a significant correlation between the depth of placental invasion on ultrasound and EBL ($r = 0.75$, $p < 0.01$). Neonates born to mothers with PAS were more likely to have lower birth weights and require NICU admission.

Conclusion: Ultrasound demonstrated high sensitivity but moderate specificity in diagnosing PAS disorder. The findings underscore the importance of combining ultrasound with other diagnostic methods to reduce false positives and optimize clinical management. The correlation between ultrasound findings and surgical and neonatal outcomes suggests that ultrasound is valuable not only in diagnosis but also in guiding clinical decisions.

Recommendations: Further research is recommended to enhance the specificity of ultrasound in PAS diagnosis, possibly through the development of more refined imaging criteria or the integration of additional diagnostic tools. Training programs for sonographers should also be emphasized to ensure consistency and accuracy in PAS detection.

Keywords: Placenta Accreta Spectrum, Ultrasound, Diagnostic Accuracy, Maternal Outcomes, Neonatal Outcome.

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Introduction

Placenta Accreta Spectrum (PAS) disorder is a severe obstetric condition characterized by abnormal placental attachment to the uterine wall, which can lead to significant maternal morbidity and mortality. The condition is classified into three grades: placenta accreta, where the placenta attaches to but does not invade the uterine muscle; placenta increta, where the placenta invades the myometrium; and placenta percreta, where the placenta penetrates through the uterine wall and may involve adjacent organs such as the bladder. The incidence of PAS has been on the rise globally, largely due to the increasing rates of cesarean

deliveries and other uterine surgeries, which are recognized risk factors for the condition [1].

Accurate prenatal diagnosis of PAS is critical for managing the condition effectively. Early detection allows for planned delivery in specialized centers equipped to handle the complex surgical interventions that may be required, thereby reducing the risk of life-threatening hemorrhage and improving both maternal and neonatal outcomes [2]. Ultrasound is the primary imaging modality used for the prenatal diagnosis of PAS due to its non-invasive nature, accessibility, and

cost-effectiveness. When performed by experienced practitioners, ultrasound can achieve high sensitivity in detecting PAS, especially when combined with color Doppler imaging [3].

Despite its advantages, the specificity of ultrasound in diagnosing PAS remains a challenge. False positives can lead to unnecessary interventions, such as cesarean hysterectomy, which carry their risks and can significantly impact maternal quality of life. Conversely, false negatives or underdiagnosis can result in unanticipated hemorrhage during delivery, potentially leading to emergencies that are not optimally managed [4]. Therefore, improving the diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound is a key focus in obstetric care.

Recent studies have aimed to refine ultrasound criteria and improve diagnostic accuracy. Advances in ultrasound technology, coupled with standardized diagnostic criteria, have enhanced the ability to detect PAS accurately. For instance, the presence of placental lacunae, loss of the retroplacental clear zone, and abnormal color Doppler patterns are now recognized as key ultrasound features associated with PAS [5]. However, the variability in diagnostic performance across different settings and practitioners underscores the need for ongoing research and training to ensure consistency and reliability in PAS diagnosis [6]. This study aims to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound in detecting PAS disorder and to assess the correlation between ultrasound findings, surgical outcomes, and neonatal health.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was carried out in the Obstetrics and Gynecology Department of a tertiary care hospital. The study was conducted over a period of 24 months.

Participants: A total of 100 pregnant women suspected of having PAS disorder based on clinical and ultrasound findings were included in the study. Participants were recruited consecutively as they were diagnosed or suspected of having PAS during routine antenatal visits.

Inclusion Criteria

- Pregnant women aged 18-45 years.
- Gestational age ≥ 20 weeks.
- Suspected or diagnosed PAS based on ultrasound findings.
- Willingness to participate and provide informed consent.
- Singleton pregnancies.

Exclusion Criteria

- Multiple pregnancies.
- Known congenital fetal anomalies.
- Women with a history of non-adherence to antenatal care.
- Participants who refused to provide informed consent.
- Cases with incomplete data or loss to follow-up.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible participants meeting the inclusion criteria during the study period were included. Diagnostic bias was reduced by having all ultrasound assessments performed by experienced sonographers blinded to the patient's clinical histories. Data analysts were also blinded to the outcomes to avoid interpretation bias.

Data Collection: Data was collected using structured case report forms (CRFs). The following information was recorded:

- Demographic data (age, gravida, parity, and gestational age).
- Ultrasound findings specific to PAS disorder, including placental location, depth of invasion, and presence of lacunae.
- Surgical outcomes including estimated blood loss, type of surgery performed, and any complications.
- Neonatal outcomes including birth weight, Apgar scores, and NICU admission.

Procedure

1. **Ultrasound Evaluation:** All participants underwent a detailed ultrasound examination by a trained sonographer using high-resolution ultrasound equipment. The ultrasound findings were recorded and used to predict the presence and extent of PAS disorder.
2. **Surgical Management:** Participants with a suspected or confirmed diagnosis of PAS disorder underwent planned delivery via cesarean section. Surgical findings were recorded, including the extent of placental invasion and any complications encountered during the procedure.
3. **Neonatal Assessment:** Immediately following delivery, neonatal outcomes were assessed by a neonatologist. Birth weight, Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes, and the need for NICU admission were documented.

Statistical Analysis: For analysis, data were imported into SPSS version 23.0. The study population's baseline characteristics were compiled using descriptive statistics. The sensitivity,

specificity, Positive predictive value, and Negative predictive value of ultrasonography were used to assess its diagnostic accuracy. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to evaluate the relationship between ultrasonography results and surgical outcomes. Using chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous variables, newborn outcomes were compared. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Results

A total of 100 pregnant women suspected of having Placenta Accreta Spectrum disorder were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 32.5 years (SD \pm 4.8), with gestational age at delivery ranging from 28 to 39 weeks (mean 34.2 weeks). The majority of the participants were multiparous (78%), with 22% being primigravida.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of the Study Population

Characteristic	Mean (SD) / n (%)
Age (years)	32.5 (\pm 4.8)
Gestational Age (weeks)	34.2 (\pm 3.1)
Gravida	
- Primigravida	22 (22%)
- Multiparous	78 (78%)
Placental Location	
- Anterior	65 (65%)
- Posterior	35 (35%)
Ultrasound Diagnosis of PAS	78 (78%)
Confirmed PAS at Surgery	85 (85%)

Diagnostic Accuracy of Ultrasound: Out of 100 participants, 78 were diagnosed with PAS disorder on ultrasound. At the time of surgery, PAS was confirmed in 85 cases, indicating that 7 cases were missed by ultrasound, and 15 cases were falsely identified. The sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV of ultrasound in diagnosing PAS were calculated.

Table 2: Diagnostic Accuracy of Ultrasound for PAS Disorder

Diagnostic Measure	Value (%)
Sensitivity	91.8%
Specificity	68.2%
Positive Predictive Value (PPV)	82.1%
Negative Predictive Value (NPV)	81.5%

Correlation of Ultrasound Findings with Surgical Outcomes: The correlation between ultrasound findings and surgical outcomes was significant. Participants diagnosed with PAS on ultrasound were more likely to have higher

estimated blood loss (EBL) and require a hysterectomy. The Pearson correlation coefficient between the depth of placental invasion on ultrasound and EBL was 0.75 ($p < 0.01$).

Table 3: Surgical Outcomes by Ultrasound Diagnosis

Outcome	PAS on Ultrasound (n=78)	No PAS on Ultrasound (n=22)
Estimated Blood Loss (mL)	2150 (\pm 580)	850 (\pm 320)
Hysterectomy Required	45 (57.7%)	5 (22.7%)
Operative Time (minutes)	110 (\pm 35)	70 (\pm 20)
Intraoperative Complications	12 (15.4%)	2 (9.1%)

Neonatal Outcomes: Neonatal outcomes were assessed immediately after birth. The mean birth weight was 2,800 grams (SD \pm 450 grams), and the mean Apgar score at 5 minutes was 7.8 (SD \pm 1.2). The need for NICU admission was higher among neonates born to mothers with confirmed PAS on ultrasound, with 40% of these neonates requiring NICU care.

Table 4: Neonatal Outcomes by Maternal PAS Status

Neonatal Outcome	PAS on Ultrasound (n=78)	No PAS on Ultrasound (n=22)
Birth Weight (grams)	2750 (\pm 460)	3050 (\pm 410)
Apgar Score at 5 Minutes	7.6 (\pm 1.3)	8.3 (\pm 1.0)
NICU Admission	31 (39.7%)	3 (13.6%)

Statistical analysis showed a statistically significant correlation between ultrasound findings and both

surgical and neonatal outcomes. The sensitivity and specificity of ultrasound in diagnosing PAS were

high, but there were notable false positives and false negatives. The correlation between the depth of placental invasion on ultrasound and EBL was strong ($r = 0.75$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that ultrasound findings can be predictive of surgical complexity. The differences in neonatal outcomes between those diagnosed with PAS on ultrasound and those without were also statistically significant, particularly in terms of birth weight ($p = 0.02$) and NICU admission rates ($p < 0.01$).

Discussion

Out of the 100 individuals, 78 patients had PAS detected by ultrasonography, and 85 cases had surgical confirmation. According to the data, ultrasound has a high sensitivity of 91.8%, which means that it can effectively diagnose PAS when it is present. The specificity, which was only 68.2%, was modest, indicating that there may have been some false-positive cases, meaning that PAS was detected on ultrasonography but not verified during surgery. This emphasizes the risk of overdiagnosing and the necessity of exercising cautious clinical judgment when interpreting ultrasonography results.

Significant correlations between ultrasonography results and surgical outcomes were also discovered by the study. Women who had an ultrasound diagnosis of PAS were more likely to need a hysterectomy and to have more estimated blood loss (EBL) after surgery. The deep placental invasion seen on ultrasound and EBL has a substantial association ($r = 0.75$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that ultrasonography is useful not only in identifying PAS but also in providing important details about the severity of the illness, which can assist surgical planning and treatment. The existence of PAS also affected the results for newborns. Compared to infants whose moms did not have PAS, newborns whose mothers had PAS confirmed on ultrasonography had lower birth weights and greater rates of NICU hospitalisation. These results suggest that PAS may have a substantial impact on the health of newborns, perhaps as a result of the necessity of an early birth and the problems that go along with it.

In a group of pregnant patients, it was evaluated the diagnosis accuracy of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and ultrasound markers for PAS. Their research showed that no single MRI or ultrasound finding could reliably and independently predict PAS. Nonetheless, the accuracy of the diagnosis was much improved when three or more ultrasonography indicators were present. Furthermore, the correlation between FIGO grading and the severity of PAS, which was made possible by the combination of ultrasound and MRI results, helped with prenatal planning and perinatal care [7].

An ultrasonographic scoring system was created by Del Negro with the goal of enhancing PAS diagnosis accuracy and forecasting newborn and maternal outcomes. According to their research, patients were correctly classified into varying PAS severity levels using the scoring method, which gives points to certain ultrasonography criteria. With a 94% diagnosis accuracy rate, our method made it easier to identify high-risk individuals and enable focused preventive measures [8].

The research findings indicate a significant correlation between intracervical lakes and severe maternal morbidities, such as major postpartum haemorrhage and the requirement for a caesarean hysterectomy. Intracervical lakes boosted the likelihood of identifying deep placental invasion and forecasting unfavourable surgical outcomes when paired with other common ultrasonography indicators [9].

Conclusion

All things considered, the study backs up the usefulness of ultrasonography in the prenatal diagnosis of PAS illness. The moderate specificity and potential consequences of false positives, however, emphasize how crucial it is to combine ultrasonography with other diagnostic techniques and clinical assessment. Further highlighting the usefulness of ultrasonography in directing clinical therapy and potentially enhancing both maternal and newborn outcomes in cases of PAS are the substantial correlations seen between ultrasound findings and both surgical and neonatal outcomes.

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